

Mizo Literary Criticism Huanga Zikpuii Pa Pawimawhna

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Mizo *Literary Criticism* bul tan leh than chhoh dan chungchang sawi apianga kan sawi hmaih leh lam hmaih loh tur chu Zikpuii Pa hnathawh leh pawimawhna hi a ni awm e. Zikpuii Pa tia kan hriat lar hi a hming tak chu K.C. Lalvunga a ni a, a pa chu Hrawva niin anu chu Lalluii a ni. Ni 27, December 1929 khan lo piangin, kum 1953 khan B.A. a zir zo a, kum 1962-ah I.F.S. (*Indian Foreign Service*) ah inziak tlingin Mizo zingah *Indian Ambassador* puitling hmasa ber niin khawvel ram hrang hrangah hna pawimawh tak chhelhin a awm kual thin a ni. A hna atanga a *pension* hnuu Mizorama an rawn let leh hnuin, nat lawk em em pawh awm lovin a chau thut a, kum 1994, October 10 khan a boral ta a ni. K.C. Lalvunga hian a thu ziak reng rengah Zikpuii Pa tia a hming a ziah vek thin avangin Zikpuii Pa tia hriat lar a lo ni ta a, Zikpuii Pa tiin kan sawi zel dawn a ni.

Zikpuii Pa hian *Criticism* huangah hian kum 1954 atang daih tawh khan kut a lo thlak tan tawh a. *Critical Works* hi kan hriat theih chinah pariat a nei a. Chungte chu, *Lushai Literature* (1954) te, *Pu Rokunga Thlirna* (1960) te, *Zosapthara Hla* (1973) te, *Kan Mizia Leb Insawiselna* (1973) te, *Mizo Rilrua Hla Hnathawh Dan* (1982) te, *Bible, Literature Hmanrapui* (1991) te, “*Ka Lungkham*” *Bu Thlirna* (1980) te, “*Lebkhabu Ramtiam*” *Bu Thlirna* (1993) te hi an ni. Heng a kut chhuak leh sulhnute avang hian Mizo *Literary Criticism* huangah hian Zikpuii Pa hian sulsutu nihna leh pawimawhna tak a nei a, chipchiar leh chiang zawkin tar lan kan tum dawn a ni.

Mizo *Literary Criticism* hian *Mizote Literature* zempuih engtik hun atang chiah khan nge bu a khuar tan tih hi sawi dan leh pawm dan pawh thlirtu hrang hrangte thlirna tlang atangin a hran theina lai a awm a. Kum 1912 khan *Bible*, Thluthlung Thar-bua Chanchin |ha an lehlin tharnaah lehlin hmasak chu a that tawh lohna laite tar langin thuhmahruaiah an dah a, hei hi thu thlitfimna lam hawi kan hmuh hmasak berah a ngaih theih a. Amaherawhchu, awmze nei leh ril tak erawh a ni lo va, a bul hrim hrim kan sawi erawh chuan heti lam hawi kan hmuh hmasak ber tia chhal ngam tur chu a ni ve thei mai awm e. Chutih lai chuan, chik zawk leh fet zawka han thlir hian, zirna huang leh khawvel huapa *Literary Criticism* pawm dan kalhmanga buklong kan khai dawn a nih chuan Zikpuii Pa-in kum 1954-a *Lushai Literature* a lo ziah hi Mizo *Literary Criticism* bul tanna tiin kan sawi thei awm e.

Lushai Literature hmanga bul tanin Mizo *Literature* huangah kum 1954 khan Mizo *Literary Criticism* chu awmze nei leh kalphung neiin a rawn vawr chhuak ta a. Mizo zingah chuan *Criticism* lam hawi awmze neia ziak hmasa ber a ni a. *Lushai Literature*-a a thlir leh sawi tam ber pawh Mizo pi leh pute thu leh hla niin, ti hian a sawi a, “Duhlian Thu leh Hla chuan mi

fate *literature* angin lo Chiang ve kher mah suh selangin, mihring lawmnaasang ber leh lungngaihna thuk berte pawh hi a lo hriatpui ve phak a ni” ti meuhin a lo hmu fiah em em a (Zikpuii Pa Hnuhma 140). Hei lo liama *literature* ropui leh hlu hi eng atangin nge kan teh chhuah chuang ang! Khawvel hnam fing leh upa zawkte *literature* nena han khaikhin ralah chuan eng teh ual ni lul lo mah se *Lushai Literature* hmanga Mizo *Literature* zahpuiawm bik loh zia min hmuh fiah tir thiam hi Zikpuii Pa ropuina leh hlutna a ni han tih loh rual a ni lo. Mizo pi leh pute hla leh sakhaw tharin a hrin chhuah hlate thiam tak leh fiah taka a han khaikhin (*compere*) kual vel leh pi pute hla hlui atanga an nunphung leh khawsak dan nen lama Chiang taka a tar lang thiam hi a bengvar thlak, Mizo *Literary Criticism* bul tanna rahbi hmasa han tih atan pawh sitawm lo tak a ni kan tithei bawkw awm e.

Zikpuii Pa-in *criticism* lam hawia a thu ziah reng rengte hi a ziah hunlai mai ni lovin, tun hnu thleng pawh hian thu ziaak tha ber ber an la ni phak hi a ropuina tak a ni a. Zosapthara hla a thlirna han chhiar phei chuan *Literature theory* chungchang pawh a hre hle niin alang a. Zosapthara bla a thlirna atanga hian J.F. Laldailova *bom sale* thlak avanga Zofate thinlunga Zosapthara ngaihniamna leh hnualsuatna awm mai tur chu huaisen taka rawn bei letin mi nawlpuiin Zosapthara hnathawh ropuina leh hlutna kan hriat thiam phak loh leh hmuh hmai zawng zawngte nen lam chuan *critical writing* hmangin Chiang leh fiah takin Zofate thinlungah a rawn pho chhuak hi a hlu ngawt mai. Zosapthara pawimawhna leh hlutna chu Chiang takin Zikpuii Pa hian a lo sawi a.

Zosapthara hi *Prose*-ah leh *Modern Poetry*-ah hian kawng sattu a ni tih a hre lo a ni. A hnathawh chu a chhia emaw, a tha emaw kawng sattu a nih hrim hrimna avang hian *History of Lushai Literature*-ah chuan minaran anga ngaih ngawt ai chuan a dinhmun chu a pawimawh fo vang (*History of Lushai Literature* te awm ngai a nih chuan). Kawng sattu hi an hmun vai en leh an thil rualrem lo nuai mam hnuu kal phei chuan, an lung khawkwaw phawh lai leh, kham kar rem lova tan an khawh laite leh an thawhrimna reng reng hi hriatthiam a har fo mai a; pa khaw hawi zau mang lo deuh tan phei chuan ‘hei chu hetia tih mai awm’ tih tih mai hi a awl viau a ni. *George Bernard Shaw* chuan a chapo ber lain, “*Shakespeare* chu kei ai chuan a ropui zawk, mahse a kokiah ka chuan avangin ani ai chuan khua ka hmu zau zawk” a ti a. Keini thangthar *Lushai Literature* sak chhoh zel tumte pawh hian, Zosapthara thlen bakkan thlen pawhin Zosapthara kokiah chuanga khaw hawi zau thei kan nihna hi theihngihl lo ila, mi fing ngaihah kan mawi zawk fovin ka ring (156).

Zikpuii Pa hian heti tak hian Zosapthara thlangang hi lo hauh na lo ta se lang, Zofate hian kan *literature* bul tanna rahbi pawimawh tak pakhat hi kan theihngihl mai lawng maw! A tlangpui thua thlirin Zikpuii Pa hian thu leh hlate hi a *literary base* lam ai chuan mihring rilru a hneh danah a teh tlangpui niin a ngaih theih a. *Grammatical form* lam ai chuan rilru chhungril lama a thawh dan leh mi a fan theih dan lam hi a chawi vul zawk zel niin a lang. Hetih rual hian hmasawanna tur kawng lamah pawh thahnem a ngai thei hle a. Kan hla thu hman leh kan hla hawi zawngte chu thlak danglam a hun tawh zia te, mahni ramri pela hnam dangte tan pawha lunglen theihna tur khawpa thu leh hla tha kan phuah a hun ve tawh zia te a sawi tel bawkw a ni.

Laldinmawia chuan heti hian a lo sawi a, “*Criticism* hi sawiselna leh a dik lo lai hailanna a ni ngawt lova, sawimawina leh hrilhfianna piah lamah a hlutna belhchhah (*value added*) chu a tum a ni thin

bawk. Khawvela ziakmi (*creative writer*) tam tak te kutchhuak hi a lo zirchiangtu (*critic*) te avanga hlu leh ropui a ni fo” (Literature Lamtluang 318). He thu hi Zikpui Pa hian *Pu Rokunga Thlirna* tih a ziah atang hian a lo man thiam hle a ni tih a hriat kan tithei awm e. Ziakmite thu leh hla hi a mawina leh ropuina te, an thu laipui leh finthuril pai zawng zawng te, a tlin tawk lohna lai leh that tawk lohna lai te hi mi nawlpuite chuan a zawng a zain kan hriat fiah loh leh kan hmuh fiah thiam loh chin a awm thin a, chung zawng zawng min kawhhuha min hrilh hre tur chuan *critic* tha an pawimawhin an hlu em em a ni. Zikpui Pa pawh hian *Pu Rokunga Thlirna* leh *Kan Mizia Leb Insawiselna*-ahte hian chiang leh fiah takin Rokunga hla thu thatna leh mawina te, mihring thinsung a nghawr nghin thei dan te, a danglamna zawng zawng te leh Thanpui Pa thlirna tlang atanga *Kan Mizia* tih *essay*-a Thanpui Pa-in a huam tir leh huam loh chin te, a huaisen zia leh a dik dan te, kan zir chhuah tur leh hriat tur te nen, a hmu fiah thiam lo ten an hmuh fiah theihna turin chiang takin a rawn tar lang iar a. Rokunga leh Thanpui pa-te a tih mawi leh ropui piah lamah, *Mizo Literary Criticism* huangah lunglu tluka thil hlu min hnutchhiah a ni kan tithei bawk awm e.

Mizo Rilrua Hla Hnathawh Dan tih hmanga Mizote rilru leh sukthlek a phawrh chhuah dan te, *Bible, Literature Hmanranpui* tih a ziah atang rigawta *Bible* nihna leh ropuina kan hriat bel zo zaite hi *Mizo Literary Criticism* huangah hian sawi bo a rem tawh lo.

Book review lamah pawh Zikpui Pa hi thil thlir thiam tak leh thlir zau tak niin, *Book review* a kalpui thin dan pawh hi a lehkhabu *review* pahnih *Lebkhabu Ramtiam’ Bu Thlirna* leh *‘Ka Lungkham’ Bu Thlirna* han thlir cheuh cheuh hian *Destructive Criticism* emaw *Constructive Criticism* emaw lam aiin *Genuine Judgement* lam rawng a pawl deuh ber niin a lang a, heng lehkhabu pahnihte hi an thatna lam ngawr ngawr emaw an tlin tawk lohna lai emaw chauh sawi lovin an thatna lai leh belchian an dawl tawk lohna laite chu sawi kawp ve vein a ngaih dan leh pawm dan a sawh nghet thiam em em a. Thangthar *Criticism* buaipui chho zel turte tan pawh mel lung pawimawh tak a lo phun a ni kan tithei ang.

Mizo Literary Criticism huangah hian mi thiamte kut chhuak leh sulnu hmuh tur hi a la tam tawk lovin, *Mizo Literature* pachhiatna ber han tih thei mai tur khawpa mite zawh loh lam tak a ni a. Chuti chung a Zikpui Pa-in kum 1954 daih tawha kawng hmang nei taka *Criticism* a lo buaipui hi *Mizo Literary Criticism* huangah chuan a hluin a pawimawh em em a, sulsutu leh kawng sattu a tling tak meuh meuh a ni kan tithei awm e.

Works Cited

- Lalthangliana, B. *Zikpui Pa Hnubma*. Published by MCL Publication, Khatla, Aizawl. Second Edition, 2000 A.D.
- Laldinmawia, H. *Literature Lamtluang*. Published by Creativentures, C-22, Karan Gharonda, Sainikwadi, Pune-411014, Maharashtra, India. 2015.